

SPICE TEAS AS FUNCTIONAL BEVERAGES: A NATURAL APPROACH TO TYPE 2 DIABETES CONTROL

¹Thammali Roshini, ²Manjari Vaka, ³K V N S Anjanee Gayatri

¹MSc., Student and Researcher and ²Project Guide ³Statistician

¹Nutrition and Dietetics and ²Assistant Professor ³Assistant Professor in Statistics

^{1&2} Department of Nutrition, Kasturba Gandhi College for Women

Hyderabad, India

Received: Jul 2 , 2025

Accepted: Jul 30, 2025

Published: Jul 31, 2025

ABSTRACT

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic condition characterized by persistent high blood sugar levels and associated issues like insulin resistance, impaired insulin secretion, and excessive insulin production. For a long time, medicinal plants have been acknowledged for their therapeutic efficacy in diabetes management, attributed to their properties that fight oxidative stress, inflammation, as well as their neuroprotective and cardiovascular advantages. Spice teas are naturally available and generally regarded in culture, especially in Asian and Indian cuisines. They are safe and provide a useful way to use medicinal plants when taken in moderation. The main objective is to determine whether there is a significant change in sugar levels before and after spice tea-based dietary intervention. A non-blind randomized interventional study was performed with 120 participants (30 in each group) who had been diagnosed with Type 2 diabetes. The subjects were separated into four groups: one control group and three intervention groups that consumed spice-infused teas (cinnamon, clove, and fenugreek). The duration of the study was one month. Data was collected through anthropometric measurements, Food Frequency Questionnaires (FFQ), and assessments of fasting blood glucose levels. Daily intake of spice teas showed a positive impact on lowering blood glucose levels. The average pre-diet sugar level was 190.63 mg/dL, which decreased to 164.73 mg/dL after the intervention, showing a mean reduction of 25.89 units. Spice-based dietary interventions demonstrated significant anti-diabetic effects. The study supports the inclusion of cinnamon, clove, and fenugreek in the diets of diabetic individuals as a natural and effective management strategy.

KEYWORDS: Diabetes mellitus, Fasting blood glucose level, Impaired fasting glucose, Spices, Herbal medicine, Anti diabetic effect, Blood sugar reduction, Clove, Cinnamon, Fenugreek.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a prevalent, but possibly fatal, medical disorder that has become more widespread in recent decades, making it a significant public health concern of the twenty-first century. (Dunya Tomic, et al., 2022). It is a metabolic disease, characterized by hyperglycemia and several other disturbances, such as insulin resistance, hyperinsulinemia, impaired insulin secretion, etc. (Calvin Ke, et al., 2022)

Many plants have long been thought to be a basic source of powerful antidiabetic medications. Medicinal herbs are used to cure diabetes, especially in underdeveloped nations, to alleviate the financial burden of conventional medications on the populace. These days, it is advised to utilize medicinal plants to treat illnesses like diabetes since they contain a variety of phytoconstituents that may have antidiabetic effects, including flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins, carotenoids, alkaloids, and glycosides. (Bahare Salehi, et al.,2019). Herbs are the green, leafy parts of plants that are used in this manner. Any portion of the plant that is not the green leafy part, such as dried bark, roots, berries, seeds, twigs, or anything else, is regarded as a spice. ((Tingqing Yu, et al.,2023)

Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*), which has been shown to have a variety of pharmacological effects, including anti-inflammatory, anti-obesity, anti-hyperlipidemic, antidiabetic, and antioxidant properties. Diosgenin, the most potent bioactive component of fenugreek seed extract, has anti-diabetic qualities. (Yamini Tak, et al.,2024)

The two main constituents of cinnamon. Cinnamon aldehyde and Trans-cinnamaldehyde (Cin), are both found in cinnamon essential oil. Cinnamaldehyde was discovered to have an anti-hyperglycemic effect via inducing the release of insulin. (Fernande Duarte Moreira, et al., 2024).

Clove spice is known to have anti-oxidant, anti-microbial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, anti-diabetic, and anti-obesity properties. Clove essential oil and extracts have a well-established anti-diabetic action. It is believed that clove extract mimics the effect of insulin on the gene expression of glucose-6-phosphatase and phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase. (Gloria Aderonke Otunola, et al., 2022)

LITERATURE REVIEW

Prawej Ansari et al. (2024) explored how plant-based diets and natural compounds can help manage diabetes and prevent its complications. With diabetes, especially Type 2, becoming a major global health concern, many people struggle with the high cost and side effects of long-term medications. The study highlights how everyday spices like cinnamon, clove, and fenugreek can support blood sugar control. Cinnamon helps by boosting insulin function and improving how cells absorb glucose. Clove not only enhances insulin sensitivity but also protects against complications like nerve and kidney damage. Fenugreek seeds have

shown promise in lowering blood sugar levels and improving insulin response. These natural remedies offer a safer, more accessible way to support diabetes care.

Ayesha S. Al Dhaheri and her associates examined potential benefits of common spices for people with metabolic syndrome, a disorder that raises the risk of diabetes and coronary heart disease, in a 2024 study. Over the course of 12 weeks, 120 participants received a daily dose of either black seed, ginger, cinnamon, or a placebo. The goal was to see if the herbs and spices helped lower blood sugar, cholesterol, and body fat. People who took the spices reported better blood sugar control and healthier cholesterol outcomes than those who received a placebo. According to the study's findings, everyday culinary ingredients may offer substantial health benefits when used in the right amounts.

Dipto Kumer Sarker et al. (2024) explored the strong antidiabetic potential of fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*), a widely used herb in Asian diets. Compounds detected in fenugreek leaves and seeds can help reduce blood sugar levels. By increasing GLUT4 activity, fenugreek improves glucose absorption, preserves β -cells, and increases insulin release, according to this assessment of preclinical and clinical data. Additionally, it lowers blood sugar-raising enzymes such as α -amylase and glucose-6-phosphatase. Improvements in lipid profiles, insulin sensitivity, and general blood glucose control were demonstrated in clinical trials. According to the study, fenugreek is a safe, natural way to manage diabetes.

Mira Syahfrien Amir Rawa et al. (2022) examined the medicinal potential of the *Syzygium* genus, which is frequently used in traditional medicine to treat memory loss, diabetes, and inflammation. *Syzygium*, a plant high in antioxidant phenolic chemicals, has potential applications in neuroprotection and Alzheimer's disease management. The study emphasized its anti-cholinesterase, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anti-diabetic qualities. By improving fat storage and glucose absorption, myricetin derivatives particularly myricitrin from *Syzygium malaccense* imitate the actions of insulin. By inhibiting ROS and inflammatory cytokines, *zygium* extracts also reduce oxidative stress and inflammation. This validates their function in enhancing insulin signalling and controlling problems associated with diabetes.

Monika Przeor et al. (2022) conducted a mini-review of typical European medicinal plants that have antidiabetic qualities. Given that 9.3% of adults worldwide suffer from diabetes, the report emphasizes the need for easily accessible, natural substitutes for pricey prescription medications. Six well-known plants are the subject of the review: *Panax ginseng*, *Phaseolus vulgaris*, *Zingiber officinale*, *Trigonella foenum-graecum*, *Morus alba*, and *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*. Scientific research has demonstrated the antidiabetic and antioxidant properties of these plants. Clinical, in vitro, and in vivo research have all demonstrated their health benefits. Type 2 diabetes may be effectively prevented and managed with the use of these natural substances.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study investigates the effect of dietary intervention in the form spice tea along with a balanced diet on Diabetes.

Data is collected via questionnaire which is modified as per the requirements of the study. The questionnaire consists of the questions on demographic details like age, education, anthropometrics which include height and weight, blood glucose levels. The main core of the questionnaire is the symptoms related to the disease, lifestyle factors, dietary habits along with food frequency questionnaire which consists of questions related to food consumption patterns. This study focuses on Type 2 diabetic patients aged 30–62 years residing in Hyderabad, selected from both diabetic clinics and community settings to ensure diverse representation and real-world relevance.

It is a non-blinded randomized controlled trial with four study groups. The target is to get 120 participants 30 under the control group and 90 under the interventional group. Information related to participants is being collected via a Questionnaire. The four study groups will receive three selected spice tea (variation 1, 2, 3) each group was given 5 grams of either cinnamon, clove, or fenugreek powder in tea form along with healthy diet while the controlled group will receive only healthy diet. It is an 1month long study where the data will be collected twice or thrice, a baseline data collection after recruiting the participants, the next set of data is collected after 15 days after the start of the intervention. All of these will be done during of follow-up sessions.

Type 2 Diabetes aged 30 to 62 years, without other long-term illnesses, Free of lactation and pregnancy and history of diabetes spanning 1–20 years are included in the study. Aged 65+ years with diabetes or its consequences, with history of severe cardiac issues, Pregnant women, Comorbidities using any form of medicines, Patients who were refused to take part in the trial, are excluded from the study.

Data analysis was done using SPSS Statistics 30.0.0.0, while data cleaning, coding, and graph construction were supported using Excel. For continuous data, descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were calculated. Regression analysis was used to evaluate the association between post-diet blood sugar levels and variables such as family history and intervention group. To assess the effectiveness of the intervention, sugar levels were compared before and after using paired sample analysis.

FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

This study investigates the effect of dietary intervention in the form of spice tea. It explores about Demographic profile, Diabetic history, Medical history including symptoms. It also evaluates about anthropometry, diet patterns, physical activity, lifestyle and support system. A sample of 120 diabetic patients was selected within the age group of 30-62 yrs.

The main goal is to determine whether there is a significant change in sugar levels before and after spice tea-based dietary intervention.

The gender distribution was about equal. All of them had Type 2 diabetes, and **56.7%** had a family history of the disease. The majority's HbA1c, which varied from 6.5 to 9.5%, suggested moderate glycemic management. **98.3%** of them were on anti-diabetic medications. There were very little side effects **2.5%**. Overweight people made up **35.8%**. This supports the association between excess weight and diabetes prevalence. Class I and II obesity rates were 25.8%. Just 35% of them had a normal BMI.

There were **85.8%** non-vegetarians. **82.5%** of people ate one to two servings of carbs per day. The majority ate either both refined and whole grains **45.8%** or refined grains **46.7%**. Just **20.8%** of people ate meals high in fibre every day. The majority of the participants routinely ate milled cereals, red gram dal, black gram, and some green vegetables. **60%** of people consumed the recommended three to four servings of fruits and vegetables each day. **40.8%** of people did not add sugar to their food, and **88.3%** ate sweets infrequently. **83.3%** of people led sedentary lives. While all participants had family support, only a small percentage had group support **4.2%** or friend support.

PARAMETER	CATEGORY	N	PERCENTAGE
Sugar Levels Before Diet	77	351	190.62
Sugar Levels After Diet	90	315	164.73
HbA1c (%)	5.6%	13.1%	8.32%
Medications Taken	0 (No)	2	1.7
	1 (Yes)	118	98.3
Type of Carbs Consumed	1 (Whole grains)	9	7.5
	2 (Refined grains)	56	46.7
	3(Both)	55	45.8
Sweets Consumption	1 (1-2 times a week)	5	4.2
	2 (2-3 times a week)	9	7.5
	3 (Rarely)	106	88.3
Typical Daily Routine	1 (Sedentary)	100	88.3
	2 (Lightly Active)	16	13.3
	3 (Moderately Active)	4	3.3

TABLE -1: Blood Parameters and Dietary Patterns of the Respondents

The paired t-test showed the average sugar levels dropped dramatically from **190.63** mg/dL to **164.73** mg/dL ($p < .001$). Regression analysis stated that while family history increased blood sugar levels, the intervention group significantly reduced them.

RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

According to the findings of this study, people with diabetes can benefit from including spices in their diets because they have strong antidiabetic effects. Family history reinforced the genetic influence on elevated blood sugar levels. Stress, diet, and physical activity remained important lifestyle factors. Despite dietary efforts and family support, problems like poor exercise habits, high consumption of refined grains, low fibre intake, and physical inactivity continue.

This study effectively evaluated the impact of spice tea dietary interventions (cinnamon, clove, fenugreek) on glycemic control among 120 individuals with Type 2 Diabetes. Based on the findings, the following **recommendations** are proposed:

- Encourage the use of spice tea as a supplemental treatment - Spice teas, especially those containing fenugreek, clove, and cinnamon, shown a statistically significant decrease in post-diet blood sugar levels. Under a doctor's supervision, diabetics may include these teas in their diets with the dosage that is advised for the relevant individuals. Bay leaves and turmeric can be added as well. It could be advantageous.
- To help with glycemic control, encourage a switch to whole grains and foods high in fibre.
- Promote Physical Activity -it is also important to note that proper diet and physical activity are of most important to keep in check of parameters. As these spices showed a decrease in glucose levels they can be used concurrently with the diet and exercise.
- Dietary changes and customized weight-loss plans ought to be given priority.
- Include techniques for reducing stress (yoga, mindfulness, counselling) and encourage information about good sleep hygiene.
- Create community-based or peer-support initiatives to improve motivation and long-term behaviour change.

Despite the positive results, this study should be interpreted in light of some limitations. The first being the small sample size of this study which is too small reduces the power of the study and increases the margin of error, a large sample size with more experimental group participants would be more reliable and provides more accurate mean values with smaller margin of error, as the current study focuses only on one geographical setting with a limited number of participants.

Teas containing fenugreek and cinnamon showed promise in lowering blood sugar levels after a diet. Despite its benefits, clove tea was associated with a few participants minor adverse effects like discomfort in the stomach.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ke, C., Narayan, K. M. V., Chan, J. C. N., Jha, P., & Shah, B. R. (2022). Pathophysiology, phenotypes and management of type 2 diabetes mellitus in Indian and Chinese populations. *Nature reviews. Endocrinology*, *18*(7), 413–432. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41574-022-00669-4>
- [2] Yu, T., Lu, K., Cao, X., Xia, H., Wang, S., Sun, G., Chen, L., & Liao, W. (2023). The Effect of Cinnamon on Glycolipid Metabolism: A Dose-Response Meta-Analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials. *Nutrients*, *15*(13), 2983. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu15132983>
- [3] Tak, Y., Kaur, M., Chitranashi, A., Samota, M. K., Verma, P., Bali, M., & Kumawat, C. (2024). Fenugreek derived diosgenin as an emerging source for diabetic therapy. *Frontiers in nutrition*, *11*, 1280100. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2024.1280100>
- [4] Moreira, F. D., Reis, C. E. G., Gallassi, A. D., Moreira, D. C., & Welker, A. F. (2024). Suppression of the postprandial hyperglycemia in patients with type 2 diabetes by a raw medicinal herb powder is weakened when consumed in ordinary hard gelatin capsules: A randomized crossover clinical trial. *PloS one*, *19*(10), e0311501. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0311501>
- [5] Otunola G. A. (2022). Culinary Spices in Food and Medicine: An Overview of *Syzygium aromaticum* (L.) Merr. and L. M. Perry [Myrtaceae]. *Frontiers in pharmacology*, *12*, 793200. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2021.793200>
- [6] Ansari, P., Khan, J. T., Chowdhury, S., Reberio, A. D., Kumar, S., Seidel, V., Abdel-Wahab, Y. H. A., & Flatt, P. R. (2024). Plant-Based Diets and Phytochemicals in the Management of Diabetes Mellitus and Prevention of Its Complications: A Review. *Nutrients*, *16*(21), 3709. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu16213709>

- [7] Al Dhaheri, A. S., Alkhatib, D. H., Feehan, J., Cheikh Ismail, L., Apostolopoulos, V., & Stojanovska, L. (2024). The Effect of Therapeutic Doses of Culinary Spices in Metabolic Syndrome: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Nutrients*, *16*(11), 1685. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu16111685>
- [8] Sarker, D. K., Ray, P., Dutta, A. K., Rouf, R., & Uddin, S. J. (2024). Antidiabetic potential of fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*): A magic herb for diabetes mellitus. *Food science & nutrition*, *12*(10), 7108–7136. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fsn3.4440>
- [9] Amir Rawa, M. S., Mazlan, M. K. N., Ahmad, R., Nogawa, T., & Wahab, H. A. (2022). Roles of *Syzygium* in Anti-Cholinesterase, Anti-Diabetic, Anti-Inflammatory, and Antioxidant: From Alzheimer's Perspective. *Plants (Basel, Switzerland)*, *11*(11), 1476. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants11111476>
- [10] Przeor M. (2022). Some Common Medicinal Plants with Antidiabetic Activity, Known and Available in Europe (A Mini Review). *Pharmaceuticals (Basel, Switzerland)*, *15*(1), 65. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph15010065>